

GitHub security for research: activity report

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Introduction

As part of our ongoing efforts to support reproducible open science at Amsterdam University Medical Center (UMC), the Research Software Management team has been developing and deploying a security infrastructure for the institutional GitHub organisation. This work addresses a concrete risk: as more researchers adopt version control in their workflows, the probability of accidental data leaks through GitHub increases. A single careless `git add .` can expose access keys and patient data to the public internet, permanently, because Git history cannot simply be deleted. This report summarises the infrastructure we have built, the security review we conducted, and what both reveal about the importance of this work.

The problem

Software version control via forges such as GitHub is now central to how research software is written, shared, and reproduced. Amsterdam UMC is actively encouraging researchers to use version control to comply with FAIR principles and institutional reproducibility and auditability requirements. This is the right direction. But it brings researchers who are unfamiliar with Git into contact with a platform that has one unforgiving property: once a file is committed, it is permanently part of the project's history. Deleting it later does not remove it. If that file contains personally identifiable data and the repository is public, it may already have been indexed or copied before anyone notices the leak. As a UMC, much of the data involved in our activities is medical in nature, aggravating the potential damage of such a leak.

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What we built: four layers of defense

In line with recommendations from OWASP², Trusted CI³, and GitHub⁴, we developed a multi-layered security infrastructure to guard against leaks of Personally Identifiable Information (PII) and access keys, such as passwords and tokens. The security infrastructure consists of four repositories and implements protection at four distinct points in the Git workflow (Figure 1), to jointly form four layers of defense.

The first layer of defense is a `.gitignore` file: every repository should include a curated list of file extensions associated with research data (such as `.csv`, `.xlsx`, `.nii`, `.dcm`, `.RData`, and `.env`), so that those files are automatically excluded from version tracking. This is the simplest and earliest line of defence, though it can be overridden.

The second and third layers of defense are provided via pre-commit and pre-push hooks. These can trigger scripts that run automatically on the researcher's own machine before a commit is saved or before code is uploaded to GitHub. They check staged files for forbidden file types, for patterns indicative of personal information (Dutch names, addresses, BSN numbers, seven-digit patient IDs), and for secrets and credentials using gitleaks, an industry-standard open-source scanner. If a violation is found, the commit or push is blocked, and the researcher receives an error message explaining what was detected and what to do next. The hooks are written in Python so that they work cross-platform, including on Windows without requiring a bash environment.

The fourth layer of defense is a GitHub Actions workflow that runs on GitHub's servers after every push. By the time this layer runs, data has already been uploaded, so it cannot prevent a leak in the way local hooks can. But it provides something the local layers cannot: it cannot be bypassed. A researcher who skips the local hooks with a `--no-verify` flag will still trigger the server-side check. When a violation is detected, the workflow dispatches an alert to a centralised telemetry repository (security-telemetry), which logs the event as a JSON file and opens a GitHub Issue for the security team to act on.

Complementing the per-repository protection is an organisation-wide scan (org-security-scanner) that runs on a weekly schedule and audits all repositories in the Amsterdam UMC GitHub organisation. This catches violations in repositories that predate the

² OWASP (2026). OWASP developer guide: Protect data everywhere (version 4.2.0). Retrieved from <https://devguide.owasp.org/en/04-design/02-web-app-checklist/08-protect-data>

³ Adams, A., Avila, K., Heymann, E., Krenz, M. Lee, J. R., Miller, B. P., Peise, S. (2023). Guide to Securing Scientific Software (version 2.0). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137009>

⁴ GitHub (2026, June 9). GitHub Docs: Best practices for preventing data leaks in your organization. Retrieved from <https://docs.github.com/en/code-security/tutorials/secure-your-organization/prevent-data-leaks>

template, or where researchers have not yet installed the local hooks. It also checks whether each repository has the required security components in place.

The entire system is distributed through a repository template (repo-template-secure) that researchers use when creating new projects. A repository created from this template has all four protection layers active by default, along with researcher-facing documentation, a structured data/ folder excluded from Git, and a SECURITY.md explaining what to do if something goes wrong.

The security logic (detection scripts, forbidden extension lists, PII reference lists, gitleaks configuration) lives in a single central repository (org-security-workflows) that all other components reference. This means that updating a detection rule or adding a new forbidden file type to the fourth layer (i.e., the GitHub Actions workflow) takes effect across the entire organisation without any changes to individual repositories.

Figure 1. The Git workflow and where each protection layer operates. Layers 1–3 run on the researcher’s computer and can prevent sensitive data from ever reaching GitHub. Layer 4 runs on GitHub’s servers after data is uploaded.

The security review

In April 2026, we conducted a full automated scan of the Amsterdam UMC GitHub organisation. The scan covered 152 repositories and checked for forbidden file types, exposed secrets and credentials, personal identifiable information, and missing security template components. The results were analysed with custom Python tooling and manually triaged to distinguish genuine issues from false positives.

The scan flagged 2,661 violations in total. After triage, some were confirmed as genuine issues requiring action; most were false positives, primarily arising from three sources: a committed Python virtual environment in one repository that generated noise across all violation categories, audio stimulus files in audiology research repositories that the

scanner incorrectly treated as data leaks, and an overly broad name-detection pattern that fired on disease ontology labels and any two adjacent capitalised words.

The confirmed issues included access keys and PII. These confirmations matter for two reasons. First, they confirm that the risks the infrastructure was designed to address are real and present in our own organisation, not theoretical. Second, they demonstrate that the infrastructure works: the scanner identified genuine data exposure that would otherwise have gone undetected, and in several cases the findings were novel enough that the repository owners were not aware of the issue.

Conclusion

The security review underlines something important about the nature of this problem. Even in a relatively small GitHub organisation with researchers who are generally conscientious, accidental data exposure happens. Patient demographic data, staff personal information, private keys, and live credentials were all found in repositories that their owners were actively using for legitimate research purposes. None of these were the result of malicious intent. They were the result of researchers working the way most people work with Git when they have not been taught otherwise: committing everything in the project folder, assuming that private repositories are safe enough, or not knowing that deleting a file does not remove it from history.

The infrastructure we have built does not eliminate this risk entirely. No technical system can. Local hooks can be bypassed. Pattern-based detection has false negatives. Researchers who do not install the hooks have no local protection. But the combination of layers, the automated weekly scan, and the telemetry system create a situation where violations are detected rather than accumulating silently, and where researchers receive immediate, actionable feedback at the moment a mistake is about to happen.

The educational dimension is equally important. The template includes documentation that explains not just how to use the system but why it exists. Clear error messages at the point of detection are more effective than warnings delivered after the fact. Researchers who understand that Git history is permanent, and who have been shown what a real data exposure looks like, are less likely to bypass the guardrails. The security review findings give us concrete, anonymised examples we can use in that education.

Discussion

Several open questions remain. A formal incident response process has not yet been defined, meaning that while violations are detected and logged, there is no agreed

procedure for who follows up and within what timeframe. Template rollout across existing repositories is underway but requires coordination with repository owners. The scanner's false positive rate needs further reduction through the improvements identified in the scan report. And a number of policy decisions about what constitutes a violation in edge cases (researcher names in public website source code, author fields in Python package metadata, eponymous disease names in ontology files) await input from ICT management and the Privacy Officer.

The infrastructure is operational and producing results. The work of the grant period has established the technical foundation. The next phase is adoption, policy, and sustained maintenance, building on its demonstrated success.

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